

Political Effects of Balkanization of SNNPRS, Ethiopia

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Received: May 06, 2025

Accepted: Jun 07, 2025

Published: Jun 10, 2025

Abstract

The configuration of the Southern Nations, Nationalities, and Peoples' Region (SNNPR) diverges from the post-1991 ethnic federalism in Ethiopia, potentially leading to the region's balkanization. A qualitative research approach was employed to select key informants purposively. The results indicate that SNNPR was established through a top-down state-making process, with no public deliberation involved. The central government pursued this creation for its own convenience. This imposition ultimately led to the fragmentation of the SNNPR into four new regional states: Sidama Regional State (CRS), South Ethiopia Regional State (SERS), Central Ethiopia Regional State (CERS), and Southwest Ethiopia Regional State (SWERS). This fragmentation has a political impact on the people of the former SNNPR, significantly diminishing their political role by marginalizing power at the federal level, exacerbating conflicts among ethnic groups, and separating adjacent ethnic groups. Therefore, before a government implements reconfiguration, it must ensure adequate participation from the concerned parties to avoid potential conflicts and tensions.

Keywords

Balkanization, SNNPR, Regions, Constitution, Conflicts

1. Introduction

Ethiopia's political discourse and governing structures have historically been shaped by its diverse ethnic, linguistic, and cultural environments. The country, home to over 85 ethnolinguistic tribes, is sometimes referred to as a "museum of peoples" (Kassa, 2021). This underscores Ethiopia's ethnic diversity, with 56 officially recognized ethnic groups (Erk & Anderson, 2009; De Villiers, 2012; Assefa et al., 2023). This diversity has significantly impacted the nation's political trajectory, particularly in relation to national integration initiatives and governance approaches.

Ethiopia was never subjected to external colonization (Aalen, 2002). However, ethnic hegemony persisted under the strategy of the indigenous imperial regime (Merera, 2004), significantly undermining regional sovereignty and excessively centralizing the state, thus fostering a uniform national identity (Beken, 2007) at the expense of diversity. The occupation, subjugation, alienation, and expansion of imperial authority into the southern, southeastern, and southwestern provinces intensified disparities (Aalen, 2002). In this context of disparities, the "national question" emerged about national oppression and the need to ensure the right to self-determination for Ethiopia's various ethnic groups (Beken, 2007). This struggle paved the way for the *Dergue*¹ regime to rise to power under a socialist system. The entire process established a foundation for implementing ethnic federalism (Aalen L., 2002; Fiseha, 2012; Cochrane & Wondimeneh, 2019; Thomas, 2016).

Despite differing philosophies, the imperial and *Dergue* administrations maintained a centralized unitary state that ignored the desires of many ethnic communities for autonomy and self-governance (Zewde, 2002). The ongoing neglect of these grievances escalated political unrest and demands for systemic reform. A pivotal moment occurred was the establishment of the Ethiopian People's Revolutionary Democratic Front (EPRDF) in 1991, marking a significant shift in the state apparatus.

The new administration aimed to reconcile local autonomy with federal power by enacting measures that promote inclusive governance and reduce interethnic conflicts (Clapham, 2006). The process began with the Transitional Charter (TC), culminating in the adoption of the 1995 Constitution of the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia (FDRE), which effectively established an ethnic federal system in Ethiopia and laid the groundwork for nine regional states (Article 47 of the FDRE Constitution), including the SNNPR. All nations, nationalities, and peoples (NNP) were granted the right to self-determination in Article 2 of the 1991 Transitional Charter as Ethiopia transitioned to an ethnic federal system under the EPRDF. However, the reorganization of SNNPR has emerged as one of the most contentious issues within this context. Multiple ethnolinguistic groups were consolidated into a single regional state during the restructuring process, violating constitutional provisions. The five transitional government regions (seven, eight, nine, ten, and eleven) established by the Charter of Transitional

¹ *Dergue* refers to the military government that existed in Ethiopia from 1974-1991. It was a leftist government usually accused of gross human rights violations.

Proclamation Number 7/1992 were merged into a single administrative entity in 1994 without the required legal and policy changes (Assefa et al., 2023). SNNPR became one of the nine regional states that comprise the federal state of Ethiopia (FDRE, 1995). The region exhibits significant disparities among its 15 million residents (CSAE, 2008; Beken, 2007), representing approximately 20% of the national population. The reference to the "Southern Nations, Nationalities and Peoples" as the architects of the constitution acknowledges the region's diverse ethnic composition and the lack of intersection of regional and ethnic boundaries (Beken, 2007). It comprises a minimum of 56 indigenous "Nations, Nationalities, and Peoples" (NNPs).

The call for self-governance through regional statehood in the SNNPR of Ethiopia highlights the need for a measured response to ensure peace, stability, and economic development (Assefa et al., 2023). The Revised 2001 Constitution of SNNPR states that the region is committed to the political, economic, and social development of its NNP. In this regard, the preamble reads as

We, the Southern Nations Nationalities and Peoples:

Decided to ensure the supremacy of the law, advance our economic and social development further to develop our language, culture, and unity, and consolidate the peace and prospect of a democratic order that our struggle and sacrifices have brought about in a Region we have established based on equality and common understanding by using our right of self-determination.

Convinced that the fulfillment of these objectives in our state requires full respect of individuals and nations, nationalities and peoples' fundamental rights and freedoms, recognition of the equality of sex, and the observance of the language and religions without any discrimination.

These paragraphs emphasize the importance of upholding the rule of law, promoting socio-economic growth, and preserving cultural unity to foster peace and democracy through self-determination. Moreover, it also emphasizes the significance of equality, fundamental rights, and non-discrimination based on gender, language, or religion in order to achieve these objectives.

However, according to Abbink (1998), the central government allegedly merged different regions into a single entity without public consultation, resulting in minimal transparency (Anderson, 2014). Moreover, Berhe and Gebresilassie (2021) assert that the 1995 merger of the five Southern regional entities into a single region was a political maneuver rather than a genuine necessity for ethnic groups to achieve self-governance. Assefa et al. (2023) asserted that establishing the SNNPRS was purely political.

Various studies indicate that internal and external factors have shaped the political, social, and economic issues in the Southern region. Regassa A. (2007) stated that the SNNPRS was

restructured to align with the ruling regime's strategic, political, and administrative goals, while Clapham (2006) and Assefa et al. (2023) assert that the merger aimed to equilibrate the preeminence of the Amhara and Oromo ethnic groups within the nation. This led to conflicts arising from an imbalance between the number of ethnic groups and the availability of local administrations (Beza, 2021). This implies that these rationales claim that the merger was a political tactic intended to promote the ruling party's interests rather than those of the Southern populace.

Balcha, (2007) also asserts that self-selected and carefully designated ethnic organizations and individuals reached a "closed-door agreement" to consolidate. The organizations and individuals involved did not represent the interests of the affected communities. They made decisions without comprehensive public input or democratic involvement despite being meant to represent the populace. This indicates that the merger process failed to reflect the community's desires genuinely and lacked legitimacy and transparency.

Therefore, shortly after its establishment, opposition arose against it and calls for creating a separate ethnic-based regional state became widespread. For example, the Sidama Council endorsed statehood in 2005, anticipating a referendum (Legide, 2019). Following the transition in 2018, several groups in SNNPRS made demands for self-administration, territorial autonomy, and administrative independence that were not adequately addressed (Regassa & Cheka, 2023). Since 2018, the 11 most populated regions—Sidama, Wolayta, Gurage, Gofa, Gedeo, Keffa, Gamo, Kambata-Tambaro, Bench-Maji, Hadiya, South Omo, and Dawro—in the now-defunct SNNP Region have collectively petitioned the regional government for referendums to attain regional state status (Ethiopian Insight, 2020). The essence of the nationalities' inquiries regarding the establishment of national-regional states involves official language, preservation of national identity, representation, political autonomy, cultural freedom, preservation of access to federal resources, and socio-economic development related to budget allocation—ultimately, self-determination. These are the intrinsic and constitutional rights of ethnic groups in Ethiopia, enshrined in both the national constitution and the constitution of the SNNP Regional State (Addis Standard, September 19, 2023).

Unlike the demands of NNPs to establish their own regional state, the administration subsequently implemented a cluster model using a top-down approach to create new regions, disintegrating SNNPRS and reorganizing it into three new regional states alongside Sidama

(Regassa & Cheka, 2023). Thus, Sidama was established in 2019. This was followed by the formation of the South West Ethiopia Peoples' Regional State (SWERS) in 2021, as well as the South Ethiopia Regional State (SERS) and Central Ethiopia Regional State (CERS) in 2023. This process resulted in the balkanization of the SNNPR. Balkanization refers to the process of breaking apart a large, multiethnic state into smaller, more ethnically homogeneous units (Bartulović, 2024; Cohen, 2003). The cluster model was, in part, an initial experiment in geographical federalism, lacking thoroughness. Anyways, SNNPR balkanized and eventually dissolved in 2023.

1. Method of the Study

The study is grounded in social constructivism, as social and political realities are diverse. This study fills the knowledge gap on the political effects of the balkanization of SNNPR. Data was gathered from both primary and secondary sources. Ten key informants from diverse political groups and eight in-depth interviews were conducted and coded to ensure anonymity. Written consent was secured from all participants. The study used purposive sampling techniques to identify resourceful persons in the four newly created regional states. A pilot test was conducted to ensure the validity and reliability of the interview questions. Given the political sensitivity of the subject, ethical considerations such as informed consent and confidentiality were given significant priority. Books, journals, Newspapers, legal documents, and policy briefs were among the secondary sources. To extract valuable insights, data collection procedures included encoding, transcription, and thematic analysis. At the same time, the discussion drew on the Instrumentalism theory of conflict as a foundational principle. It discusses how elites and counter-elites within ethnic groups select aspects of the group's culture, attach new values and meanings to them, and use these symbols to mobilize the group, defend its interests, and compete with other groups (Kataria, 2018). This study reveals the political effects of balkanization on the people of the former Southern Nations, Nationalities, and Peoples' Region (SNNPR).

2. Political effects of balkanization

Sidama was founded as a mono-ethnic region, whereas CERS, SERS, and SWES were established as cluster-based regional states following the reorganization of SNNPR. This shift suggests that localized, identity-based conflicts have increased in southern Ethiopia, contributing to the process that led to changes in the political-administrative structure. Contextual modifications have intensified interstitial frictions, awakened dormant claims, and realigned

ethnic power equations, as they have generated borderland disputes despite their apparent intention to support claims for self-determination and promote administrative efficiency. Indeed, historical disputes, resource conflicts, and elite competition combine to create a form of estrangement that, far from settling issues, makes it difficult for societies in multi-ethnic contexts to pursue reconciliation.

2.1 Marginalization at the federal level

Challachew (2023) notes that the collapse of SNNPR signifies the loss of collective bargaining strength among regional elites for the federal government and governing party. Since 2018, following the arrival of a new government in Ethiopia, the political role of the Southern Peoples in the federal government has undergone significant changes. According to key informants, the number of individuals in important political positions was encouraging during the EPRDF era; however, it has diminished considerably with the transition to the Prosperity Party (PP). Informants suggest that the PP views the Southern People as sympathizers of the former Tigray People's Liberation Front (TPLF), leading to a reluctance to allocate an adequate number of positions to them. This reduction affects not only political leadership roles but also extends into the military sector. Veteran military personnel in Wolaita Soddo shared that the military is facing pressure from the political party, forcing him and his colleagues to retire solely because they were from the South. He expressed that they had served the country with intense patriotism and commitment from a very young age, yet they were compelled to retire without receiving the respect they deserved. However, the Ministry of Defense has frequently stated that it is implementing military reform, which includes human resources, finance, technology, and the chain of command.

The second political role that the Southern Ethiopian people have diminished due to balkanization is the loss of key political positions at the federal level, according to the informants. For instance, until the 2018 political change in the country, the chairperson of the ruling party, EPRDF, was Haile Mariam Desalegn. His party leadership role stems from the chairing of the Southern Ethiopian Peoples' Democratic Movement (SEPDM), which was the southern satellite of the EPRDF. Therefore, he was a Prime Minister. According to Article 72/1 of the Constitution of FDRE, the Prime Minister is vested with the highest executive powers of the Federal Government, along with the Council of Ministers. However, practically, the Prime Minister holds nearly all power in the country. Haile Mariam Desalegn, the former Prime

Minister of Ethiopia, was from South Ethiopia, a member of the House of People's Representatives from Wolaita, and the head of SEPDM. Moreover, core political positions, such as the Minister of Defense and the Minister of Education, were held by Southern Ethiopian Peoples according to the informants. Currently, however, the Southern Ethiopian peoples are relegated to marginal positions in the Ethiopian political system.

The third aspect of the political effect of the balkanization of SNNPR on Southern peoples, according to Ethiopian Insight (2020), is that it undermines collective bargaining power at the federal level by eroding the harmony and unity of Southern Peoples in federal politics. This is substantiated by key informants indicating that the people from the southern region, due to their shared affiliation with the SNNPR and the SEPDM, used to work together with 'southern psychology,' which, in their view, played a significant role in shaping the Ethiopian political system. However, the new leadership intentionally expedited the fragmentation of SNNPR to diminish the influence of the Southern peoples in national politics, according to informants. One of the areas where southern peoples made significant losses was particularly within the House of Federation (HoF). According to Article 61/2 of the FDRE Constitution, each NNP shall be represented in the House of the Federation by at least one member and by an additional representative for every one million of its population. This establishes the preeminence of Southern populations, as the region comprises a large number of ethnic groups. In justifying this, Habtu (2004) notes that

the SNNP regional state, comprising forty-six ethnic groups, has fifty-four representatives in the House of Federation, the upper house of the FDRE. The Tigraway, the politically preeminent ethnic group, possesses three Members of Parliament. In contrast, the Oromo and Amhara, the two largest ethnic groups, have nineteen and seventeen lawmakers, respectively. Notably, neither Addis Ababa nor Dire Dawa, two multiethnic federal regions, are represented in the House of Federation.

This implies how Southern peoples used to have a dominant political role at the federal level. According to Article 62/7, the HOF possesses considerable authority, including the allocation of income from joint Federal and State tax sources, the Federal Government's subsidies to the States, as well as handling self-determination issues as per Article 62/3.

Without institutional guarantees for inclusion, the political reengineering of the southern region underscores the shortcomings of ethnic federalism. Ethiopian ethnic federalism was founded on the principles of solidarity and autonomy; however, trends since 2018 indicate a shift toward centralization under the guise of ethnic division. The situation in the South exemplifies how,

ironically, fragmentation can reduce rather than enhance the agency of historically marginalized groups, transforming ethnic identity from a source of political mobilization into a tool of control. It is essential to contextualize the observed marginalization within the broader framework of state-building in multiethnic nations. The deliberate use of fragmentation to undermine regional cohesion aligns with the postcolonial government's "divide and rule" theories, which suggest that central authorities aim to prevent regional alliances from developing into rival power centers (Aalen, 2006; Asnake, 2009). This approach may yield short-term political stability for the governing party. However, it carries the risk of long-term dissatisfaction, elite alienation, and the resurgence of regional autonomy or independence movements.

2.2 Exacerbating Conflicts among ethnic groups

Informants from the three multi-ethnic regional states indicate that new forms of hatred and conflict are emerging in these newly established regions. For instance, in southern Ethiopia, tensions and animosities persist between the Wolaita and Gamo peoples among the residents of the two zones. This situation began with the announcement of cluster centers in the region. When Wolaita Soddo was declared the political and administrative center of SERS, political figures from the Gamo side encouraged civilians to protest against the decision, resulting in exchanges of offensive remarks between activists from both groups. Informants from the Wolaita side suggest that Gamo politicians acted this way, at least in part, to secure the presidential position as compensation for losing the political center. Blagojevic (2009) noted that politicians exploit ethnic differences by drawing upon historical memories of grievances and "whipping up" hatred in order to gain or strengthen their power. Conversely, Gamo politicians accuse senior Wolaita politicians of persuading Prime Minister Abiy to designate Wolaita Soddo as the political and administrative center of the region.

According to informants from both sides, there is currently a great deal of hatred, mistrust, and similar feelings among the political figures from both sides. Since no adequate intervention has been made so far, tensions are increasingly polarizing between the two groups, and there is potential for conflict among them. However, the problem lies in the zero-sum politics of the federal system over the past three or four decades, where regional state capitals receive all the political and economic advantages at the expense of their outskirts. Administrative geography becomes a surrogate for the broader ethnic contestation in this context, and the symbolic capitals

serve as sites of struggle over belonging and legitimacy. At the same time, the mismanagement of social media today is exacerbating the conflict between the two.

The other type of conflict observed following the balkanization is the Zeyse–Gamo dispute. Borders and borderlands present opportunities for individuals and groups while simultaneously hindering social and economic relations due to competition and varying governmental systems. The Zeyse–Gamo dispute, which ignited after the establishment of SERS in 2023, poses a considerable security threat to the newly formed region. Since October 2023, it has resulted in the fatalities of 11 civilians, several injuries, extensive internal displacement, property devastation, and widespread arbitrary arrests of ethnic Zeyse individuals (Regassa & Cheka, 2023). The struggle originates from the enduring aspiration of the Zeyse for a self-governing, separate woreda, according to the Ethiopian Peace Observatory (May 28, 2025). This movement was revived during the post-2018 national political shift alongside several other autonomy movements in SNNPRS. The Zeyse–Gamo conflict exemplifies a tendency in SERS and nationwide about top-down regional reconfiguration, which incites disputes over boundaries and borderland resources. According to the recent reports from the Ethiopian Peace Observatory (28 May 2025)

On 11 May, unidentified gunmen ambushed three patrols carrying South Ethiopia regional police officers in Zeyise Demibele kebele — also known as Hawsha kebele — in Arba Minch Zuria woreda, Gamo zone. The attack could be connected to the Zeyise community’s request for self-administration. Members of the Zeyise community residing in the area want to separate from the Gamo zone and establish their own special woreda, granting them the same status as a zone. The special woreda status would enable the community to respond directly to the regional administration instead of the zone-level administration. Following the 11 May ambush, local security forces launched an operation that resulted in at least five reported fatalities. On the following two days, security forces reportedly killed three civilians, injured an unidentified number of people, and burned and destroyed several houses in Zeyise Demibele kebele. In Zeyise Elgo kebele, regional security forces beat and detained an unspecified number of Protestant worshipers who were mainly from the Zeyise ethnic group at Mulu Wengel Church. Due to the unrest in these kebeles, residents stayed home for days, fearing the violence would escalate.¹ On 18 May, the anti-riot police of the South Ethiopia regional state shot and killed two ethnic Zeyise farmers in Zeyise Demibele kebele who ventured outside their homes to search for missing cattle. Meanwhile, the Gamo zone police said no fatalities occurred during the operation, which they called “an operation to capture bandits.

This implies that severe measures are being taken against the Zeyse ethnic groups, who are entitled to establish their own self-administration, which is constitutionally guaranteed.

Moreover, the Gamo–Zeyse instance illustrates competition for borderland resources as a causal factor driving identity-related political demands (Regassa & Cheka, 2023). The affair is not merely an administrative squabble; it has its roots in historical grievances over land, control of banana-producing lands, and a longing for autonomy. The contention regarding the banana-abundant borderland between the Gamo and Zeyse, which the Zeyse assert as their ancestral territory, is primarily a resource issue, leading Gamo elites to stifle the Zeyse's pursuit of autonomy, particularly following the establishment of SERS. This resulted in the politically motivated exclusion of populations in the borderlands in ethno-resource terms. According to the informants, the Zeyse's call for zonal status is part of the broader pattern seen among small ethnic groups demanding special zones as a guarantee of their rights in the country's federal system. However, between the federal and regional governments' heavy-handed security approaches, which have included arrests and extrajudicial killings, these incidents have only added to the delegitimizing of the state's attempts to mediate conflicts, and public trust remains hugely eroded.

The case also suggests that the top-down approach to regional reconstitution, often masquerading as reform, has led to governance failures and intra-regional breakdown. Given the Zeyse call for restructuring, this did not reflect an institutional discussion but rather coercion, further marginalizing them. These trends validate criticisms that have been raised for years, indicating that Ethiopia's brand of ethnic federalism, which lacks strong inter-group consensus-building and conflict-mitigation mechanisms, turns identity into a battleground rather than an instrument for coexistence.

Disagreements were not only prevalent in SERS but also in CERS, such as the Kabena–Gurage conflict. The Kabena–Gurage conflict highlights concerns regarding land expropriation amid urban expansion, which has an ethnic dimension. Wolkite town has become a focal point of controversy, particularly following the founding of CERS in 2023 and the establishment of the 2012 town plan (Regassa & Cheka, 2023). The establishment of CERS as a cluster region through a top-down methodology and the contested master plan for Wolkite town have raised significant questions regarding the land claims made by the Kabena and the Gurage.

The clashes over land grabs are directly attributed to the expansion of cities and serve as a flashpoint for inter-ethnic violence in Ethiopia. According to the informants, the Kabena people's rejection of the 2012 master plan and its reaffirmation in 2023 underscores the

increasing perception that regional reorganization legitimizes the eviction of landowners by powerful entities, often without proper notification or compensation. In such contexts, ethnic identities can be used to regulate access to property, governance, and urban amenities, thereby creating structural inequities that heighten tensions. The establishment of CERS identified Wolkite as one of the administrative centers of the new region, thereby raising the likelihood of urban expansion and land confiscation from Kabena farmers in the surrounding areas, as informants reported. The master plan for Wolkite, which the Kabena have contested since 2002 due to its inclusion of historic Kabena territories, has intensified tensions between the factions.

These incidents illustrate that rather than reducing ethnic tension, the creation of new regional states has exacerbated it. The restructuring process is based on elite compromises, opaque decision-making, and a lack of effective mechanisms to resolve conflicts, which has not met the continued demand for recognition and self-government, resulting in micro-nationalisms, reduced inter-ethnic solidarity, feelings of exclusion, and mistrust. The failure to establish inclusive institutions or anticipate the politics of cluster-based formations risks solidifying grievances that could trigger further violence.

The role of social media cannot be overlooked in these disputes. Stemming from the early conflicts of the 1990s, particularly in Rwanda and Bosnia, authors have examined the role of the media in ... promoting conflict ... (Schoemaker & Stremlau, 2014). In the absence of effective state-led communication or reconciliation processes, online platforms have been used by activists and elites to mobilize ethnic sentiments and spread narratives of hostility, thereby transforming local rivalries into identity-based crises, according to the informants. This marks a dangerous intersection of ethnic mobilization and information disorder, worsened by institutional indifference. These instances highlight a significant contradiction within the Ethiopian federal structure, a tension between ensuring autonomy and centralizing authority, which is compounded by ineffective implementation, resulting in a paradox of empowerment and marginalization. Without established mechanisms for internal dialogue and equitable distribution of resources and power, Ethiopia's federal framework risks fragmenting into a confederation of contested sovereignties.

2.3 Separated adjacent ethnic groups

The regional disintegration has negatively impacted the political networks of all peoples, but it has had a greater influence on relations between neighboring groups. For example, the

relationship between Gedeo and Sidama, as well as Wolaita and Dawro & Konta. According to Brunner (1996), the disposition toward national [ethnic] intolerance can be strengthened by new political leadership if the leaders lack the necessary political sense of responsibility and succumb to the temptation of diverting attention from pressing socioeconomic problems by creating national concepts of enemies. This presents a significant opportunity for the forces of the new regimes, who either lost power or feared losing it. According to informants, the re-drawing of regional boundaries in post-2018 Ethiopia, the dismantling of the SNNPR, and the formation of cluster-based regions have produced a paradoxical twist in which aspirations for local autonomy have inflamed inter-ethnic fissures and disrupted existing relationships between neighboring groups. Federalism in Ethiopia was initially established to manage diversity and ensure that NNP have self-rule. However, the recent state-making adjustments have strained relations among neighboring groups and displaced peoples, intensifying local-level competition for political power and access to economic resources, according to the in-depth interview in Gurage.

According to informants, the Gedeo and Sidama peoples are not only closely related in culture and identity but also share long-standing boundaries and have significant populations in each other's territories. The boundary line between Sidama and Gedeo is less than a kilometer from the downtown area of the capital city of Gedeo, Dilla. That is why Sidama and Gedeo were initially anticipated to be clustered together as a region (Ethiopian Insight, 2020). However, due to the rejection of the former, Gedeo has no boundary line with the people of South Ethiopia, forcing them to travel long distances, which raised administrative costs for the people, according to an in-depth interview. The transitional charter places Gedeo alongside Sidama in Region 7 (Negarit Gazeta, 1992). However, the Sidama regional state formation occurred unilaterally—without integration with the Gedeo—marginalizing the Gedeo, as they ended up with an incongruous relationship with people 500 kilometers away in South Omo in administrative terms. Such a reorganization has increased manorial costs, alienated the Gedeo people, and reduced their share in regional politics and access to institutional power centers.

The second area where the creation of new regional states has harmed interethnic relations, according to key informants, is between Kaffa and Dawro. Both ethnic groups were part of Kaffa Kiflehager during the Derge period before Dawro joined the Omotic groups in Semen Omo. Although both are Omotic groups, Dawro shares language intelligibility and cultural similarities with the Wolaita, Gamo, Gofa, and Konta peoples, in contrast to the Kaffa, who have a different

language (Zewde, 2002). Proclamation Number 7/1992 also included Dawuro among the peoples of Wolaita, Gamo, Gofa, Konta, and others. When regional clustering emerged as the only option during the dissolution of the SNNPR, Dawuro politicians chose to revert to the structure of the Derg period and align with Kaffa and other southwestern Ethiopian peoples (Ethiopian National Election Board, 2021). However, currently, there is significant disagreement between the two sides regarding power-sharing and regional office placements. According to key informants, Kaffas, who are the majority in the Southwest, are dissatisfied with the power distribution that allowed Dawuro to become the president of the region. Additionally, key sector offices were planned to be located in Tercha, the capital of Dawro. However, Bonga, the center of Kaffa, was left unoccupied. This conflict has escalated to the grassroots level, resulting in instances of interpersonal tensions in Tercha and Bonga.

The links between Dawro and Kaffa have also weakened due to strategic disjunctions and elitist accommodations following the founding of the SWEF. Although both groups were historically merged within the same administrative unit under the Derg, their allegiances have diverged since 1991— with Dawro aligning with the Omotic cluster to the north and Kaffa aligning with its southwestern neighbors. The re-grouping of Dawro with Kaffa, in a retrogressive manner, was not based on historical or cultural understandings, but rather on political and elite interests. The resulting power-sharing struggles have escalated bottom-up tensions, eroding communal relationships that were previously less contentious. Political entrepreneurs contribute to the creation and reinforcement of ethnic polarization in society (Bartulović, 2024).

What is particularly alarming is the general refusal of current Ethiopian federalism to consider these specific geographic, cultural, and socio-economic proximities instead of being politically constructed by elites. The crisis is further exacerbated by the issue of administrative capital, which has proven to be a contentious topic. As suggested by the new economic geography (Krugman, 1996), the designation of regional capitals plays a significant role in urban development, infrastructure investment, and public sector employment, especially regarding business opportunities. Areas and factions excluded from these capitals or whose proximity to established alliances has been disrupted experience increasing economic vulnerability and political alienation. Recent studies have empirically documented the varying impacts of administrative proximity on economic opportunities. Egger et al. (2022) and Turner (2014) found that employment opportunities and infrastructural development are directly related to closeness

to administrative centers. Bluhm et al. (2021) also found that the location of political capital leads to positive spillovers across neighboring regions. The choice of administrative capital in the Ethiopian context is as much symbolic as it is a material part of intergroup competition and perceived ethnic bias or favoritism.

Compounding the tragedy is the absence of transparent and participatory leadership in the region's reform process. Informants repeatedly cite these as the crucial issues that compound a lack of trust, favoritism, poor communication, and deals driven by the elite. Had the clustering procedure been consulted whilst respecting spatial contiguity and cultural affinities, the regional states could have been a source of cooperation rather than disintegration. This quick-hit, top-down approach has turned closeness to want.

The fragmentation of the SNNPR, with redrawn internal boundaries, has not resulted in viable federal units based on ethnic self-determination. Instead, it has produced politically volatile, economically erratic, and socially disjointed regional sub-units with inadequate internal cohesion for sustained governance. The ongoing clashes among tribes, such as Gedeo vs. Sidama, Dawro vs. Kaffa, and land disputes in the Gurage and Kebena areas, illustrate that spatial and political engineering should be contextual. Moreover, if this fails, the dissolution of the region would exacerbate past grievances and incite new rounds of marginalization violence.

2.4 Conclusion

Ethiopia is an ancient state that European powers have never colonized. However, domestic occupation, conquest, and oppression led the people of the country to resist the imperial regime. After these ongoing struggles, the country transitioned from a unitary to a federal system. This federal system was established based on the country's constitution, which proclaimed the right to self-determination for the NNP of Ethiopia. The NNP became the holder of sovereign power in the country.

The formation of SNNPR has been contentious from the very beginning, unlike other regional states in Ethiopia, where various ethnic groups were compelled to merge and coexist. This situation led the NNP to demand its own self-governing region, resulting in the fragmentation of SNNPR, which includes Sidama, South Ethiopia Peoples' Regional State, Central Ethiopia Peoples' Regional State, and Southwest Ethiopia Peoples' Regional State.

However, fragmentation itself has political effects on people in various parts of the former SNNPR. The Southern people lost their political role at the federal level, as they were pushed to the periphery, where they once held significant positions. Furthermore, the new reconfiguration has sparked conflicts and, in some areas, resulted in fatalities. The Gamo-Wolaita tension following Wolaita Sodo's rise as the political and administrative center of SERS has led to opposition from Gamo elites, and the effects persist. The most severe situation is the Zeyse-Gamo conflict, which centers on the Zeyse people's quest for self-determination. The Keben and Gurage conflict around Wolkite town over ownership of the town and its surrounding land has resulted in disputes among the people of the region. Therefore, state fragmentation and reconfiguration lead to persistent conflicts; new regional states should be established through public consent and discussion rather than imposition.

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